

The Journal of the Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies, Faculty of Arts
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

LEAD CITY JOURNAL OF RELIGIONS AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

(ISSN 3043-4416)

Editorial Chief Consultant:
Anjola ROBBIN, PhD

Editor-in-Chief:
Ayodele Adeyinka ATOWOJU, PhD

Corresponding Editor:
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD

Emergence of a New Terrorist Group “Lukarawa” in Northwest Nigeria and Its Implications on the Peaceful Coexistence and Religious Harmony of People in the Region

Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD

Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
afolaranmi.adebayo@lcu.edu.ng, +2348055159591, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8057-137X>

Abstract

Nigeria and many other countries of the world are struggling to curtail the spread of terrorist groups in their areas. However, recently, another terrorist group known as “Lukarawa” (or “Lakurawa”) emerged in northwest Nigeria thereby threatening the peaceful coexistence and religious harmony of the region and other parts of the country. This paper aims to examine the causes of the emergence of this new terrorist group, its ideology and activities, and its implications on the peaceful coexistence and religious harmony of people in the region and other parts of the country. The study explored a systematic literature review method interacting with existing literature and some reports from print media. The theoretical framework used in this study is Functionalist Theory. It was discovered that the emerging terrorist group was initially a pro-people group but later started unleashing terror on the people of northwest Nigeria. Traditional and regional leaders have begun looking for ways to curb the group's activities. The Nigerian security operatives are not left behind in the efforts. It is therefore recommended that religious leaders, traditional leaders, as well as security agencies should strive to curb the activities of the group before they escalate to full-blown terrorism in the region and other parts of the country.

Keywords: “Lukarawa” or “Lakurawa”, Terrorist Groups, Northwest Nigeria, Peaceful Coexistence, Religious Harmony, Violent Conflicts, Armed Banditry

Introduction

Terrorist groups and other forms of violent conflicts and criminality have become activities that many governments throughout the world are combatting currently (Olanrewaju, Folarin, & Folarin, 2017). Many

countries of the world are struggling to curtail the spread of terrorist groups in their regions (NATO, 2024). Nigeria, as a country, is not exempted from these struggles (UNODC, 2024). A notable terrorist group in Nigeria in particular is Boko Haram – a group that “has been implicated in numerous bombings, suicide bombings, kidnappings, murders, arsons, and willful destruction of property in Nigeria and her neighboring nations” (Lawal & Dauda, 2023). This terrorist group concentrates its nefarious activities in the northeastern part of Nigeria (Afolaranmi, 2020). As the Nigerian government is battling with the violent activities of this group, another terrorist group known as “Lukarawa” or “Lakurawa” emerged in the northwestern part of the country specifically “in Sokoto and Kebbi states, threatening critical governance strides in these subnational enclaves” (Achi, 2024). Being a new group, few scholarly studies have been done on this group. Therefore, this paper aims to examine the emergence of this new insurgency group, their activities thus far and the implications of the terrorist group on the peaceful coexistence and religious harmony of people in the region, and then give some recommendations on how to curb the activities of the group.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is Functionalist Theory propounded by Durkheim. This is a theory that views terrorism through the lens of sociology. It is believed that social norms are important in countering terrorism as some rebellious individuals in the society violate the laid down rules and procedures. So, there is a need for social change to combat these deviant behaviours. Anytime there is an intrusion or shock through terrorism on any society, it is believed that the anticipated reaction is to resist or intervene through laws or institutions and adherence to rules and regulations of a given society (Abuloye, 2024).

Emergence of “Lukarawa” Terrorist Group

The term “Lukarawa” or “Lakurawa” (as scholars and reporters interchangeably refer to it) may likely be a Hausa-ization of the French word for “the recruits” (*les recrues*) (Barnett, Rufa’i, & Abdulaziz, 2022). “Lukarawas” is not a new group as some people would want to believe as it has been in existence since 2018 (or even earlier) “when the group started helping locals fight armed gangs known as bandits” (Reuters, 2024). The group believed to be a set of herders was initially invited by the local traditional leaders to fight armed bandits (Ojo & Olumba, 2024). Rufa’i (2023) had earlier reported this by asserting that the locals initially invited the group for protection. By this, the group was considered pro-people till some people started accusing it of “stealing their cattle and seeking to impose strict Islamic law” (Reuters, 2024). However, recently the Nigerian Defence Headquarters through its Director of Defence Media Operations, Maj. Gen. Edward Buba, confirmed the (re-)emergence of the terrorist group in the northwestern part of the country as a new terrorist group (Ige, 2024). According to the army general, “the group originated from the Sahel region, particularly Mali and Niger, after last July’s [2023] coup in Niger disrupted joint military patrols along the Nigerian border” (Obiezu, 2024). Whichever was the origin of the group, it is gradually gaining prominence in print and social media as it is increasing its nefarious activities in the region.

Figure 1: “Lukarawas” terrorists (Source: Mohammed, 2024)

Ideology and Activities of “Lukarawas”

“Lukarawa” group is linked to Jama’at Nusrat al-Islam wal-Muslimin (JNIM), an al-Qaeda franchise in Mali (Barnett, Rufa’i, & Abdulaziz, 2022). As cited above, the main interest of the “Lukarawa” group is to impose strict Islamic law on the people. This is not surprising as religion has taken a prominent role in fueling violent conflicts in the northern part of Nigeria (Mercy Corps, 2022). This has made Lawal and Dauda (2023) give some recommendations on how to use religion, especially Islamic religion, to curb insurgency in Nigeria.

It was reported that the “Lukarawa” group permeated northwest Sokoto and Kebbi States from neighboring Niger and Mali after the 2023 coup in Niger (Obiezu, 2024). The group “armed with sophisticated weapons, has been operating in Gudu, Tangaza, Binji, Illela, and one other local government area, imposing its beliefs on the populace” (Ige, 2024). Being associated with other terrorist groups like ISIS, this new terrorist group is reported to “want to forcefully impose their brand of Islam; punishing people for shaving their heads and for listening to music, like the Taliban of Afghanistan, and waging war on security and government officials who they see as obstacles to their ideology” (Ado, 2024). The group killed fifteen people in Mera village, Augie Local Government Area of Kebbi State as they were preparing for Jumaat prayers on Friday, November 8, 2024 (Ahmadu-Suka, Auwal, & Adebayo, 2024). It was also reported that this group has attacked other villages by imposing financial levies on these communities and stealing food crops and livestock (Etim, 2024).

Efforts to Curtail “Lukarawa” Terrorist Group

Sequel to recent killings of people and disruption of peace in northwest Nigeria, the Arewa Consultative Forum (ACF) has admonished the security agencies to take rapid and decisive action to eliminate the Lukarawa Terrorist Group before it gains more ground in the area and other parts of the country (Etim, 2024). This call has led Nigerian

security agencies to swing into action by making efforts to curb the activities of the terrorist group (Odeniyi, 2024). Time will tell whether this action by the security operatives will yield positive results.

The Implications of the “Lukarawa” Terrorist Group on the People

Insurgents and terrorists have been great threats to the peaceful coexistence and religious harmony of people wherever these evil perpetrators operate (Bell, et al, 2024). Boko Haram (a notorious terrorist group in northeastern Nigeria) initially started bombing churches and attacking Christians. The group now targets mosques and Muslims as well especially those that are against its ideology (Husted, 2022). The group has disrupted the peaceful coexistence of people and rendered many people homeless and displaced (Afolaranmi, 2020). Bandits and other perpetrators of violent conflicts in the northwestern part of the country have disrupted and killed many Muslims in their mosques during prayers (Kitabu, 2022). This new “Lukarawa” terrorist group may perpetrate more evils in its bid to enforce its strict Islamic law on people if care is not taken. Living in this area and worshipping in mosques and churches may become dangerous and unsafe if the group is allowed to operate without resistance. Other terrorist groups may emerge if “Lukarawa” terrorist group is allowed to operate freely in the region and other parts of the country.

Conclusion

There is no gainsaying to say that the new terrorist group “Lukarawa” or “Lakurawa” is posing a great threat to the peaceful coexistence and religious harmony of the people of northwest Nigeria. The group is attempting to impose strict Islamic law on the people, and causing mayhem in the region. By so doing, the group is disrupting the peaceful coexistence and religious harmony of these people. This was how Boko Haram started in the northeast Nigeria. The Lukarawa group may

become another nightmare to the people and the government of the day if it is not addressed decisively.

Recommendations

Against the background of the conclusion above, these recommendations are made:

1. Religious leaders (especially Islamic religious leaders) should rise up and disown this group and its activities and so-called “strict Islamic” ideology;
2. Government and other security agencies should be decisive in confronting this group without fear or favour;
3. Traditional and community leaders should cooperate with government and other security agencies to fish out this group and should not harbour it in any way in their communities;
4. Land borders with neighboring countries should be more secured to prevent invasion from unwanted foreigners who may want to come in to unleash terror on the law-abiding citizens of the country;
5. Scholars and other stakeholders in peace and conflict studies should study further on this new group and come up with further recommendations on how to combat it.

References

- Abuloye, Ayoola (2024). Theoretical Framework for Terrorism and Counter-Terrorism: The Nigeria Experience. *Beijing Law Review*, 15, 394-405. <https://doi.org/10.4236/blr.2024.151025>
- Achi, Louis (2024, November 12). Lukarawa Threat: Sokoto Braces, Maintains Development Strides. *ThisDay*. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2024/11/12/lukarawa-threat-sokoto-braces-maintains-development-strides/>
- Ado, Emmanuel (2024, November 12). Sokoto state and the Lukarawa security challenge. *Blueprint Newspapers Limited*. <https://blueprint.ng/sokoto-state-and-the-lukarawa-security-challenge/>
- Afolaranmi, Adebayo Ola (2020). "Faith-Based Interventions in the Reintegration of Displaced Boko Haram Victims into the Society: A

Review of Selected Literature". *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 6(8), August 2020, 297-314.
<https://doi.org/10.36713/epra4986>

- Ahmadu-Suka, Maryam, Abubakar Auwal & Ismail Adebayo (2024, November 11). ACF urges action as Lakurawa kills 15 in Kebbi. *DailyTrust*.
<https://dailytrust.com/acf-urges-action-as-lakurawa-kills-15-in-kebbi/>
- Barnett, James, Murtala Ahmed Rufa'i, & Abdulaziz Abdulaziz (2022). Northwestern Nigeria: A Jihadization of Banditry, or a 'Banditization' of Jihad? *CTC Sentinel*, 15(1), 46-69. <https://ctc.westpoint.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/CTC-SENTINEL-012022.pdf>
- Bell, Kabiru Ilelah, Adlina Ab Halim Mohd, Mahadee Bin Ismail Mohd, Sabri Md Nor Mohd, Sabri Md Nor (2024). "Exploring the Implication of Communal Violence on Peaceful Coexistence and Security Governance in Bauchi State, Nigeria". *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(10), 1735-1756.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v14-i10/23278>
- Etim, Etim (2024, November 14). Lukarawa: President's word matters. *TheCable*. <https://www.thecable.ng/lukarawa-presidents-word-matters/>
- Husted, Tomás F. (2022). Boko Haram and the Islamic State West Africa Province. *Congressional Research Service (CRS)*.
<https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/IF10173.pdf>
- Ige, Olugbenga (2024, November 7). DHQ confirms emergence of new terrorist group in Sokoto, others. *Punch*. <https://punchng.com/dhq-confirms-emergence-of-new-terrorist-group-in-sokoto-others/>
- Kitabu, Mohammed Umar (2022). "Effect of Banditry on Socio-Economic Development of Niger State". *Lapai International Journal of Administration LIJAD*, 5(1), 48-67.
- Lawal, Manzoor Apenna & Oluwaseun Kazeem Dauda (2023). Religious Insurgency and The Quest for Sustainable Peace in Nigeria: The Islamic Model as A Panacea. *Indonesian Journal of Interdisciplinary Islamic Studies (IJIIS)*, 6(2), 103-125. DOI: 10.20885/ijiis.vol6.iss2.art1.
- Mercy Corps (2022). 'FEAR OF THE UNKNOWN': Religion, Identity, and Conflict in Northern Nigeria (July 2022). *Mercy Corps*.
https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2021-07/FearoftheUnknown_Full_6-30-21.pdf
- Mohammed, Sani Danaudi (2024, November 12). The Lukarawa: Time for Decisive Action in Northern Nigeria. *Wikki Times Media and*

- Publishing Ltd. <https://wikkitimes.com/the-lukarawa-time-for-decisive-action-in-northern-nigeria/>
- NATO (2024, July 25). Countering terrorism. *North Atlantic Treaty Organization*.
https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_77646.htm#:~:text=This%20of%20field%20can%20relate%20directly,terrorist%20acts%20involving%20CBRN%20substances.
- Obiezu, Timothy (2024, November 8). Security analysts concerned as Nigeria warns of new terror group. *VOA*.
<https://www.voanews.com/a/security-analysts-concerned-as-nigeria-warns-of-new-terror-group/7857317.html>
- Odeniyi, Solomon (2024, November 13). DHQ moves to stop Lukarawa's recruitment drive. *Punch*. <https://punchng.com/dhq-moves-to-stop-lukarawas-recruitment-drive/>
- Ojo, John Sunday & Ezenwa E. Olumba (2024, November 17). Nigeria's terror group Lakurawa is nothing new – it exists because of government's failure: analysts. *ModernGhana*.
<https://www.modernghana.com/news/1357618/nigerias-terror-group-lakurawa-is-nothing-new.html>
- Olanrewaju, Faith O., Oluwafunke M. Folarin, & Sheriff F. Folarin (2017). Insurgency and National Security Challenges in Nigeria: An Introductory Analysis. *Ante Portas – Studia nad Bezpieczeństwem*, 2(9), 35-53.
- Reuters (2024, November 11). Who are the Lakurawa insurgent group threatening Nigeria? *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/who-are-lakurawa-insurgent-group-threatening-nigeria-2024-11-11/>
- Rufa'i, Murtala Ahmed (2023). "Analysing the Response of Traditional Authorities to Muslim Youth Extremism in the Nigeria-Niger Border Areas of Sokoto State." In David Ehrhardt, David Oladimeji Alao, M. Sani Umar (eds). *Traditional Authority and Security in Contemporary Nigeria*. London: Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003428596>
- UNODC (2024). SUPPORTING NIGERIA IN ITS STRUGGLE AGAINST TERRORISM. *United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime*.
https://www.unodc.org/conig/uploads/documents/UNODC_TECHNICAL_ASSISTANCE_IN_NIGERIA_FINAL.pdf